

CORROSION PROTECTION OF MMCs BY DIAMOND-LIKE CARBON COATINGS

B. Wielage, A. Dörner

Institute for Composites and Surface Technology, TU Chemnitz, D-09107 Chemnitz, Germany

SUMMARY: Carbon fibre reinforced aluminium exhibits a poor resistance against electrochemical corrosion in 3.5 wt.% NaCl solution. Diamond-like carbon (DLC) coatings provide properties which make them interesting materials for external corrosion protection on metal matrix composites (MMCs). The electrochemical corrosion behaviour of uncoated and DLC-coated carbon fibre reinforced aluminium is tested in 3.5 wt.% NaCl solution. It has been found that the pitting potential is shifted significantly in the anodic direction and the corrosion current density is much lower due to the presence of the sealing DLC-coating. Additionally, scratch tests and SEM-studies were carried out in order to characterise the adhesion of the DLC-films on the heterogeneous MMCs. Reliable corrosion protection is connected with a sufficient coating durability under loading. In order to ensure the loading capacity of the DLC-coating under tribological conditions wear tests were undertaken which reveal a considerable improvement of the wear resistance due to the deposition of the DLC-coatings.

KEYWORDS: carbon fibre reinforced aluminium, diamond-like carbon, plasma deposition, electrochemical corrosion, surface modification, metal matrix composites

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) possess improved properties in comparison to the base metal counterparts such as higher temperature operating limits, increased and tailored strength and stiffness, good thermal conductivity, abrasion and creep resistance as well as dimensional stability. However, before this materials merit serious consideration for a wide range of applications, not only reliable data on mechanical properties, but also detailed information about the corrosion behaviour in relevant environments are necessary.

The present paper gives results about corrosion protection of carbon fibre reinforced aluminium by surface modification of the MMCs due to the deposition of a diamond-like carbon (DLC) coating. Corrosion protection by external coatings relies not only on the chemical properties and the density, but on good durability and wear resistance of the coating under loading conditions. Therefore, additional wear and scratch tests were carried out on the DLC-coated MMCs.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Deposition of the DLC-coatings

Diamond-like carbon coatings were deposited on unidirectionally carbon fibre reinforced aluminium by plasma deposition. Before generation of the DLC-films, the substrates were polished to a 1 μm finish and ultrasonically cleaned in ethanol. The substrates were placed in the working chamber, negatively discharged, and cooled. After an additional in-situ cleaning by bombarding with Argon ions, the generation of the DLC-coating took place using a direct current discharge and benzene as gaseous precursor under a pressure of between 0.005 and 0.05 Pa.

Characterization of the DLC

Raman spectroscopy is an important method for analyzing carbon films due to its ability to distinguish between different bonding types and domain sizes. DLC-films exist in a variety of different structures and compositions. Therefore, the shape and the peak positions of the DLC Raman spectra may be different in dependence on the deposition technique, the process parameters, and the substrates. The 514.5 nm radiation of a 100 mW Argon-ion laser was focused to a round approximately 2 μm spot. The tested DLC spot was optical checked with a microscope using a magnification of 1000. There was no degradation of the DLC visible under this conditions. The Raman spectra were excited at a temperature of 22 ± 2 °C under laboratory conditions by using a back scattering geometry without polarization analysis.

In order to determine the hardness a Vickers type diamond indenter was loaded against the DLC surface to a maximum load of 10 mN at a loading rate of 1 mN s^{-1} , and the hardness was determined under load. The indentation depth of the Vickers diamond was less than one-tenth of the DLC-coating thickness. Ten measurements were carried out on each specimen in order to get representative data, and the mean values as well as the standard deviation were calculated.

Scratch test

Scratch testing is used to evaluate the adhesion between the DLC-coating and the substrate. In addition, this test provides information on residual stresses within the coating and about failure mechanisms. During the test a progressively increasing load ranging from 0 to 20 N was applied to a diamond indenter at a rate of 10 N min^{-1} . Three parallel scratches were applied to each specimen. Acoustic emissions during scratching were recorded. The assessment of this emissions and the optical evaluation of each scratch in the microscope gives information about the coating damage.

Wear test

The tribological behaviour of the DLC coated MMCs was investigated by means of a sliding wear equipment. Consisting of a turning cylinder which is pressed on to the samples surface with a constant force. The cylinder has an internal diameter of 5 mm, an external diameter of 7 mm, and consists of hardened steel C 100 W1 (62 HRC). During the wear test a sliding speed of 0.47 ms^{-1} , an pressure of 1.06 MPa, and 30 min testing time were chosen. All sliding wear tests were performed at room temperature and in laboratory air. The wear intensity can be calculated from the depth of the wear track and the whole length of sliding path.

Electrochemical corrosion test

Samples for the electrochemical tests were cut into about 1 to 2 mm disks. In order to ensure the exposure of a similar surface area to the corrosive electrolyte samples are embedded in an epoxy resin. Current flow took place over a conducting wire which was soldered on the back of the sample and completely covered by the epoxy resin. The embedded disks without the

DLC-coating were polished to a 1 μm finish, while the DLC-coated MMC-samples were tested without any further mechanical or chemical surface treatment. All samples were rinsed repeatedly in distilled water and cleaned ultrasonically in the same medium before the potentiodynamic corrosion test. The corrosion tests were carried out in pH neutral 3.5 wt.% NaCl solution. The electrolyte was not moved or aerated. Before the potentiodynamic test the samples were allowed to stabilize at their corrosion potential for at least 1 hour. After this time the polarization started from the corrosion potential in the cathodic direction with 0.1 mV s^{-1} . Finally, after reaching -1500 mV the polarization was turned in order to record the anodic branch until at least -500 mV were reached. The in following presented measurement results are an average of at least three corrosion tests. Further information were given by the assessment of the exposed surfaces in the scanning electron microscope (SEM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterisation of the DLC-coating

Since Raman spectroscopy provides information on types of chemical bonding, it is widely used in characterisation of DLC-films. The Raman spectrum of the DLC-film is shown in Fig. 2. Generally, there are two broad bands at approximately 1550 (G band) and 1355 cm^{-1} (D band) for DLC [1]. Amorphous carbon films consist of clusters of threefold coordinated sp^2 carbon embedded in a sp^3 -bonded carbon matrix. While the sp^2 clusters are responsible for properties like the optical gap, the sp^3 clusters determine mechanical properties, for example the hardness of the DLC. The scattering around the G band is attributed to well-localized sp^2 -coordinated anomalies. A shifting of the G line peak to higher wave numbers is considered as evidence for the tendency of the film to be more graphite-like [2]. Table 1 contains results obtained from 10 Raman spectra of DLC on carbon fibre reinforced aluminium. The intensity ratio of the D band to the G band calculated from this data is about 1,9. Another important feature of DLC is the hardness. As stated in previous publications [3] the hardness of the DLC-films is in the range of between 17 and 24 GPa.

Table 1: Raman spectra of the DLC

	<i>PEAK POSITION [cm^{-1}]</i>	<i>PEAK WIDTH</i>	<i>PEAK HEIGHT</i>
D PEAK	1307 \pm 19	269 \pm 34	5 \pm 2
G PEAK	1532 \pm 26	138 \pm 29	5 \pm 2

Scratch test

The results from the scratch test reveal good adhesion of the DLC to the aluminium and the carbon fibres [3]. No deadhesion of the DLC-coating was detected under the chosen test parameters. Investigations of the scratch traces by SEM exhibit crack formations within the DLC. This varifies cohesive failure within the DLC and indicates that the cohesive bonding within the DLC is lower than the interfacial adhesion between DLC and aluminium or DLC and carbon. A reason for the cohesive damage in the DLC could be high intrinsic stresses which may be due to the bombardment by energetic species with high energies, thermal contraction during the cooling or the incorporation of hydrogen.

Wear test

The sliding wear resistance of the DLC-coated MMCs is increased by a factor of ten in comparison to the uncoated substrates [3,4]. A lot of investigations indicate the generation of

a transfer layer during the sliding wear of DLC [5-9]. Kim et. al. [7] argued that the hydrogen contained in DLC-films has an important role in influencing the tribological behaviour since it passivates the dangling bonds and permits only weak interaction between the contacting surfaces. The combination of a hard surface with a lubricating transfer film is considered as ideal for sliding wear protection. Furthermore, the coating support from the MMC substrate is an essential feature and a necessary condition to use the material under high wear loads. The wear trace within DLC-coated unreinforced aluminium shows a damaged DLC-coating. Under the chosen sliding wear conditions the DLC-coatings is cracked. This indicates an intensive plastic subsurface deformation under the acting wear loads. On the other hand, no cracks within the DLC-film were observed on the coated MMCs, which is an evidence of an improved coating support from the substrate due to the reinforcement of the soft aluminium with the carbon fibres.

Electrochemical corrosion

In dependence on the surrounding environmental conditions electrochemical corrosion could arise to a serve problem for MMCs. As exhibited in Fig. 1, the sensitivity of reinforced metal against electrochemical attack is increased due to a variety of different influences.

Fig. 1: Variety of influences on the electrochemical corrosion behaviour of MMCs

To assess the corrosion performance of MMCs correctly it is important to take all these influences into consideration. In general, with increasing heterogeneity the sensitivity to electrochemical corrosion is believed to be enhanced. In addition, in the case of carbon fibre reinforced aluminium (C/Al-composite) both components are highly electrically conductive. Therefore, the galvanic effects increase the corrosion rates. Residual stresses are a factor for stress corrosion. Especially after processing by a liquid metal infiltration or a thermal cycling of the MMC, residual stresses could be present due to the high differences of the thermal expansion coefficient of carbon fibres and aluminium. Crevice corrosion may occur on the fibre-matrix interface or within matrix defects such as pores. Both the interface and the microstructure of the matrix are dependent on the processing route and parameters. During the processing a reaction between the fibres and the metal may occur resulting in the formation of interfacial phases. In the case of a C/Al-composite this reaction product is Al_4C_3 . Fig. 2 exhibits a TEM micrograph of the fibre-matrix interface within a C/Al-composite. As visible, the Al_4C_3 -needles grow with an angle of about 45° to the fibre surface and obtain an average size of about $0.5 \mu m$. Because there is only local formation of carbide needles, no brittle behaviour of the interface is observed, but very good load transfer from the matrix into the fibres can be expected.

Fig. 2: Fibre-matrix interface with Al_4C_3 before the corrosion test, TEM

Finally, the changed conditions of the oxide film on the aluminium matrix could be responsible for a higher sensitivity against electrochemical attack. Corrosion data of these composites which were received from the potentiodynamic corrosion test in 3.5 wt.% NaCl solution are shown in Table 1 and were discussed in previous publications [10,11]. It should be pointed out again that the overlapping of the pitting and the corrosion potential of pure unreinforced aluminium is caused by the calculation of the mean values and the standard deviations. In every single potentiodynamic curve the pitting potential is about 20 mV more positive than the corrosion potential for the unreinforced aluminium samples. However, for the C/Al-composites the pitting potential is indeed more negative than the corrosion potential. It means that the pitting corrosion starts without the external polarization of the MMCs. This fact illustrates once more the strong decrease of the corrosion resistance caused by the reinforcement with carbon fibres. The reason for this effect could be that changes in the composition of the protective oxide layer took place, and it may be expected that the reinforcement tends to degrade the integrity of this protective oxide layer on aluminium.

Table 2: Electrochemical data in 3.5 wt. % NaCl

<i>MATERIALS</i>	E_{CORR} [mV]	E_{PITT} [mV]	i_{CORR} [$\mu A cm^{-2}$]
Unreinforced aluminium	-752 \pm 6	-739 \pm 10	1,0 \pm 0,3
C/Al-composite	-757 \pm 8	-764 \pm 8	14,9 \pm 0,8
Unreinforced aluminium + DLC-coating	-754 \pm 1	-505 \pm 4	0,2 \pm 0,1
C/Al-composite + DLC-coating	-758 \pm 1	-524 \pm 6	0,8 \pm 0,4

In Table 2 the corrosion data of C/Al-composites with the DLC-coating are exhibited. The fractured cross-section of a DLC coated C/Al-composite is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: DLC-coating on fibre reinforced aluminium, SEM

DLC-coatings influence the electrochemical corrosion behaviour of aluminium and C/Al-composites considerably. Although, the deposition of the DLC-coatings with the used technique and parameters effects the pitting potential and the corrosion current density, no shift of the corrosion potential could be detected. This may be attributed to the presence of defects like pinholes (Fig. 4) within the DLC-coating which allows the electrolyte to contact the substrate. Although, the DLC is an isolating barrier coating and covers up the MMC and aluminium surface, there are apparently still substrate sites which are exposed to the electrolyte. Therefore, the corrosion potential of the DLC coated materials has the same value like that of the uncoated substrates. For the DLC coated unreinforced aluminium the corrosion current density is reduced by a factor of five compared to uncoated aluminium. For the DLC coated C/Al-composites the corrosion current density is smaller than that of uncoated MMCs by a factor of 15. These data indicates an improved corrosion resistance. However, one has to take into account that the real current density in the uncovered defects is much higher than the in Table 1 presented data. This is the case because the corrosion current density is calculated with the geometrical exposed, but actually mainly covered area.

As shown in Table 2, the pitting potential is shifted approximately 250 mV to more positive values. This fact also could again be related to the nearly complete sealing of the surface area by the DLC. The anodic metal dissolution remains controlled by the transport rate of the electrolyte to the substrate over a much wider range until there is a sharp increase in the corrosion current density beyond about – 500 mV. That means, from this potential the anodic metal dissolution is enhanced significantly. A promoting influence for the occurrence of a sharp pitting potential may be the formation of corrosion products at the DLC-substrate

interface. The interface is under corrosive attack within the coating defects. Not only the aluminium is dissolved, but corrosion products may force the DLC-coating to deadhere. In that case a much bigger area of the substrate is exposed to the corrosive environment. SEM investigations confirm film deadhesion at higher potential. Figure 5 reveals an area with dramatic film deadhesion. As visible, the aluminium matrix is dissolved completely in the surface region. Only the carbon fibres seem to remain.

Fig. 4: Defect within the DLC-coating after the plasma deposition, SEM

Fig. 5: Coating deadhesion after the corrosion test, SEM

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) The DLC-coatings influence the electrochemical corrosion behaviour of aluminium and carbon fibre reinforced aluminium considerably. Although, the deposition of the DLC-coatings with the used technique and parameters effects the pitting potential and the corrosion current density, no shift of the corrosion potential could be detected. This may be attributed to the presence of coating defects such as the observed pinholes which allow the electrolyte to contact the substrate.
- (2) The DLC-coating provide good protection for the aluminium and the carbon fibre reinforced aluminium during short term exposure in 3.5 wt. % NaCl solution. The suitability of DLC-coatings as a long term corrosion protection on these materials has to be investigated in future research. Coating defects or damage due to mechanical impacts, for example during tribological loading, are considered to be critical in terms of coating deadhesion. The formation of corrosion products on the DLC-substrate interface may accelerate the DLC deadhesion.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Dr. C. Schürer (GFE e. V. Schmalkalden, Germany) is gratefully acknowledged for the deposition of the DLC-coatings and helpful discussions. In addition, the authors wish to thank Dr. J.-H. Kim and Scott Jewhurst (Materials Department, University of California at Santa Barbara).

REFERENCES

1. S. Zhang, B. Wang, J. Y. Tang, "Processing and characterisation of diamondlike carbon films", *Surface Engineering*, Vol. 13, 1997, No. 4, pp. 303-308
2. Cooper, C. V., C. P. Beetz, B. W. Buchholz, P. J. Wilbur, R. Wie, "Spectroscopic and selected mechanical properties of diamond-like carbon films synthesized by broad-beam ion deposition from methane", *Diamond and Related Materials*, Vol. 3, 1994, No. 4-6, pp. 534-541
3. Wielage, B. and A. Dorner, "Bonding and sliding wear behaviour of diamond-like carbon coatings on fibre reinforced aluminium", *Surface & Coatings Technology*, Vol. 108-109, 1998, pp. 473-478
4. Wielage, B. and A. Dorner, "Diamondlike carbon coatings on fibre reinforced aluminium", *Surface Engineering*, Vol. 4, 1998, No. 5, pp. 413-417
5. Yoon, E.-S., H. Kong, K.-R. Lee, "Tribological behaviour of sliding diamond-like carbon films under various environments", *Wear*, Vol. 217, 1998, pp. 262-270
6. Miyoshi, K. J. J. Poch, S. A. Alterovitz, "Plasma-deposited amorphous hydrogenated carbon films and their tribological properties", *Mater. Sci. Forum*, Vol. 52-53, 1989, p. 645
7. Kim, D. S., T. E. Fusher, B. Gallois, "The effect of oxygen and humidity on friction and wear of diamond-like carbon films", *Surf. Coating Technol.*, Vol. 49, 1991, pp. 537-542
8. Gupta, B. K. and B. Bhushan, "Micromechanical properties of amorphous carbon coatings by different deposited techniques", *Thin Solid Films*, No. 270, 1995, pp. 391-398
9. Yamada, H., O. Tsuji, P. Wood, "Stress reduction for hard amorphous hydrogenated carbon films deposited by self-bias method", *Thin Solid Films*, No. 270, 1995, pp. 220-225
10. Wielage, B. and A. Dorner, "Einfluß einer Faserbeschichtung aus pyro-Carbon auf das elektrochemische Korrosionsverhalten von Kohlenstoff/Aluminium-Verbunden", *Materials and Corrosion*, 49, 1998, pp. 428-434
11. Wielage, B. and A. Dorner, "Charakterisierung von Metall-Matrix-Verbundwerkstoffen auf Leichtmetallbasis", in: *Tagungsband I. Werkstofftechnisches Kolloquium Chemnitz*, B. Wielage (ed.), Verlag Mainz, Aachen, 1998, pp. 119-131